

Fundamental Mathematical Analysis of Transaction-based Law and Economics

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Abstract

Investigating the base ground of economic growth as a mathematical model is an essential economic issue. Every economic entity does economic behaviors to maximize its goal, total utility, in a given time. By bringing out the premises of the game theory, market participants, transactions, and market entities-related agents are defined. Next, concerning the general regional economy, the transaction model in the market participants could be set. And finally, a law and economics notion to set a model of economic growth would be drawn.

1 Introduction

A good decision refers to a decision when making a decision in which a previous decision influences a subsequent decision with an economic benefit. Therefore, when exploring time-to-time choices, the goal is to pattern laws for the types of decisions that occur in reality.

In physics, these interactions are set by a commonality as observations. And by symmetrical conservation, potential and kinetic parts of energy differentiate. This paper will demonstrate that this phenomenon applies same with the law and economy as a mathematical framework, especially from transactions to economic growth.

2 Modeling

2.1 Decision - Game Theory

The foremost premises of observation in physics could be derived from the game theory[1]. These premises would be interpreted again in the context of economics here.

2.1.1 Construction of Game Theory

Like in most situations, humans have both rational and irrational decisions. Game Theory specifies on which occasion humans make biases in making decisions, as repeating what has been discussed in observation within physics.

- Rule of transaction
 - Market participant - In the real economy, a market participant tries to minimize irrational judgment to maximize rational judgment.
 - Transaction order

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- * Concurrent or sequential transaction - In the real economy, the superiority and inferiority of decisions in deciding the order of the transaction at the same time or sequentially affect the transaction.
- Knowledge and information the market participant knows during the transaction
 - * Knowledge through the history of the transaction - In the real economy, the less knowledge market participants have, the more they fall into error until they make a complete decision.
 - * Knowledge by publicity of transaction - There may be different meanings in the real economy, no matter the decision.
 - * Knowledge inequality in the transaction - In the real economy, greater marginal utility can be created due to grounds that others could not consider at the time of the transaction.
- Strategy of transaction
 - Formation of strategy - In the real economy, transaction occurrence may prioritize one opportunity rather than based on calculation probabilities.
- Result factors of transaction
 - Consequences of the market participants' actions - In the real economy, beyond the expected utility hypothesis's explanation, market participants sometimes make wrong decisions by mistaking themselves for rationality.
 - Distribution of the benefit by transaction - In the real economy, there is always a difference in the distribution advantage of profits when making decisions for all people.

Given the limitations of existing game theory, it can be said that market participants in the real economy have the following selection characteristics.

1. Market participant tries to minimize irrational judgment to maximize rational judgment.
2. The superiority and inferiority of decision in whether to decide the order of the transaction at the same time or sequentially affect the transaction.
3. The less knowledge market participants have in the transaction, the more they fall into error until they make a complete decision.
4. : No matter the decision, there may be different meanings.
5. Greater marginal utility can be created due to grounds others could not consider during the transaction.
6. Transaction occurrence may prioritize one opportunity rather than based on calculation probabilities.
7. Market participants sometimes make wrong decisions by mistaking themselves for rationality.
8. There is always a difference in the distribution advantage of profits when making decisions for all people.

2.1.2 Two Types of Transactions and Determinants in Market

Strategic factors that can be adjusted during the transaction environment are:

- Decisions about time affect how market participants respond to differences in their internal profit-sharing dominance.
 - (Law of Time 1) Reduce distortion of internal profit-sharing dominance among market participants
- Decisions about time affect agreement on details among market participants
 - (Law of Time 2) Decisions made at the right time led to undisputed agreement on details among market participants

For the individual transaction, it takes an approach like this.

$MP = \text{Market Participant}$

$TP = \text{Total Population}$

$MP = \{\text{Market Entity } ME \mid ME \subset \{\text{Person } P \mid P \in TP\}\}$
 $= \{ME_1, ME_2, ME_3, \dots, ME_{N(MP)} \mid ME_n \text{ is } n \text{ th order to share profit of } MP\}$

Total utility from a transaction equals the sum of individual utilities, which is the sum of separate transaction utilities.

$T = \text{Transaction}$

$TTU_{MP,T} = \text{Total Utility by Transaction } T \text{ of Market Participant } MP$

$ITU_{ME,T} = \text{Individual Transaction } T \text{ Utility of Market Entity } ME$

$\text{Lorenz}_{MP,ME} = \text{Individual Utility Distribution Rate} = \frac{ITU_{ME,T}}{TTU_{MP,T}}$

$$TTU_{MP,T} = \sum_n^{N(MP)} TTU_{ME_n,T} \cdot \text{Lorenz}_{MP,ME_n}$$

Law of Time 1, 2 means that transaction total utility differs in time, and the market participant wants to make a transaction in time when the total utility from a transaction gets maximized.

$$t_{MP,wanted}^* = \text{Desired period of a transaction for } MP$$

$$= \arg \max_t TTU(T, t)$$

Extensive-form game is a game about successive times in one space. The factors that can be adjusted during the transaction environment are:

- Decisions about where to do transactions affect the superiority and inferiority between the competitors
 - (Law of Space 1) Each market participant tries to advance the transaction in the most advantageous position for themselves.
- Decisions about where to do transactions affect the default competitors to consider superiority and inferiority
 - (Law of Space 2) The weak competitors aim for the weakest point of the strong, and the strong competitors prefer the place where their strengths are most evident as the transaction location.

The market is a space where transactions are placed in. And transactions happen in a market where the total sum of market participants' utility in a specific period gets maximized.

$$\text{Market } M = \{T \mid T \text{ is a transaction}\}$$

$$\forall (\text{Transaction } T) \in \arg \max_M \sum^{N(\{MP \vee MP\})} TTU_{MP,T}$$

Accordingly, the factors that can be adjusted during the transaction progress environment are as follows. And in a real economy market, both a strategic game and an extensive game are played simultaneously. So, addressing this in the market, it can be applied as follows.

- Time Law 1 + Space Law 1 - A market participant may interfere with the opponent's choice of a preferred transaction location to reduce the internal profit share of the opposite market participant.
 - A market participant may interfere with an opponent's preferred market choice to undermine the other market participant's internal profit share.
- Time Law 1 + Space Law 2 - A market participant may lower the opposite market participant's internal profit share to prevent the opposite market participant from choosing a preferred transaction location.
 - A market participant may lower the internal profit share of the other market participant to impede the other market participant's preferred market choice.
- Time Law 2 + Space Law 1 - The market participant tries to select a place other than the opposite market participant's preferred transaction place based on the transaction details' confirmation.
 - A market participant would like to select a market other than the market favored by the other participant based on ascertaining the market details.
- Time Law 2 + Space Law 2 - A market participant may wish to confirm the transaction details via a location other than the opposite market participant's preferred transaction location.
 - A market participant may wish to establish a market other than the market preferred by the other participant.

By Time Law 1 + Space Law 1, Time Law 1 + Space Law 2, internal profit distribution is related to total transaction utility. And by the preceding subject is a market structure that forms a relation between internal profit distribution and total transaction utility. We will assume this type of market structure of a market entity in a mapping function MST at period t applies to the relation of internal profit distribution $Lorenz_{MP,ME}$ and total transaction utility $TTU_{MP,T}$.

By Time Law 2 + Space Law 2, Time Law 1 + Space Law 2, choice of the market where transaction placed can relate to internal profit distribution $Lorenz_{MP,ME}$.

The market structure comprises a set of rules R . Rules are for sustaining the market itself.

$$R = \{r \mid r \text{ is a rule set in } \exists M\}$$

$$0 \leq MST_t(M, R)$$

According to the preceding premise, through the premise of game theory, we will classify them as follows:

- Fallacy of perception
 - (Rule 3) The less knowledge market participants have in the transaction, the more they fall into error until they make a complete decision.
 - (Rule 7) Market participants sometimes make wrong decisions by mistaking themselves for rationality.
- Fallacy of memory
 - (Rule 4) There may be different meanings no matter the decision.
 - (Rule 5) Greater marginal utility can be created due to grounds others could not consider during the transaction.
- Fallacy of opportunity
 - (Rule 1) Market participant tries to minimize irrational judgment to maximize rational judgment.

- (Rule 6) Transaction occurrence may prioritize one opportunity rather than based on calculation probabilities.

Market participants' perception, memory, and opportunity fallacy cause distortions in time and space. In the real economy, it's about assessing transactions that could be placed in. According to Rules 7, 5, and 1, These fallacies make transactions to be placed in not in the highest Total Transaction Utility $TTU_{MP,T}$. On the other hand, according to Rules 3, 4, and 6, these fallacies' effectiveness changes over time.

Rule 7 is about a market participant MP . Rule 5 is about a transaction T . Rule 1 is about a market entity ME , and by that TTU and $Lorenz$ is affected.

First, the market entity relation between TTU and $Lorenz$ is affected by the probability of falling into the fallacy of opportunity. So, what is the fallacy of opportunity? It is a tendency to get more than what market participant is allowed. We will assume that T_{oe} is a transaction with opportunity fallacy.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Opportunity fallacy probability function } OE(T) = \\ p(\{T_{oe} \mid T_{oe} \text{ is a transaction when } \frac{\text{observed } ITU_{ME,T}}{\text{observed } TTU_{MP,T}} > Lorenz_{MP,ME}\} \mid^{\forall} T) \end{aligned}$$

Secondly, the transaction is affected by other interactions. So, what is the fallacy of memory? It is a tendency to synchronize with what is natural, which is less than what should be accurate. We will assume that T_{me} is a transaction with opportunity fallacy.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Memory fallacy probability function } ME(T) = \\ p(\{T_{me} \mid T_{me} \text{ is a transaction when } \frac{\text{observed } ITU_{ME,T}}{\text{observed } TTU_{MP,T}} < Lorenz_{MP,ME}\} \mid^{\forall} T) \end{aligned}$$

Thirdly, the transaction is affected by the market participant's internal decision of individual distribution. The fallacy of perception is a tendency to distort the internal utility distribution by market participants' arbitrary perception. We will assume that T_{pe} is a transaction with perception fallacy.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Perception fallacy probability function } PE(T) = \\ p(\{T_{pe} \mid T_{pe} \text{ is a transaction when } \frac{ITU_{ME,T}}{TTU_{MP,T}} \neq (\text{observed } Lorenz_{MP,ME})\} \mid^{\forall} T) \end{aligned}$$

So, Total Transaction Utility with the considerations of discussions above can be in form like this:

$$\begin{aligned} TTU_{MP,T} = \sum_n^{N(MP)} MST(MP, ME_n, M) \cdot TTU_{MP,T} \cdot Lorenz_{MP,ME_n} \\ \cdot (1 - OE(T))(1 - ME(T))(1 - PE(T)) \end{aligned}$$

2.1.3 Concealment of Reality With Offering Agreeable Compromise

In reality, the transaction opportunity is given every time, and the strategy is constantly exposed to the opponent. Therefore, concealment of behavior is the best way to disperse the predictability of operations exposure. This creates an error term so that the opposing market participant cannot know their strategy as much as possible.

For this, the two methods can be alternated randomly.

- Clear perception of reality or exposure of honest operational descriptions
- Unclear perception of reality or exposure of arbitrary operational descriptions

This essentially protects the market participant's opponent from reading the strategy of the operation. It can also provide incentives by offering compromises through a resolution to the transaction opponent. By preemptively presenting one's own goals, the other market participants reduce their resource consumption through the transaction as much as possible and take incentives for consensus.

Offering compromises through a resolution also requires two things in mind.

- It may happen that opponents avoid negotiating until the end of the transaction even though the chances of victory are small. At this time, whether the transaction should continue should be judged based on the utility obtained from the negotiation.
- A market participant may not give their opponent the same opportunity throughout a transaction. For this reason, market participants must know in advance what the opponent wants and decipher the situation accordingly. In other words, the market participant needs to give the other market participants the minimum possible consensus point that is universal to each other.

In other words, according to the transaction strategy, offering compromises are needed to reduce the waste of resources while concealing the action.

According to the upper discussion, concealment of strategy is a cost(CC_t) that has a limit bound for a transaction that can be used in maximizing the benefit of the following transaction in period t . On the other hand, offering compromises can be a benefit(OC_t) that has a limit bound for a transaction that can be used in maximizing the benefit of the current transaction in period t . That makes the gap between the actual transaction total utility from the currently wanted transaction utility.

$$\begin{aligned}
TTU_{MP,T} &= \sum_n^{N(MP)} MST(MP, ME_n, M) \cdot TTU_{MP,T} \cdot Lorenz_{MP,ME_n} \\
&\quad \cdot (1 - OE(T))(1 - ME(T))(1 - PE(T)) \\
Optimal\ t_{wanted}^* &= \arg \max_t TTU_{MP,T} \\
Optimal\ t_{actual}^* &= \arg \max_t (TTU_{MP,T} - CC_t + OC_t) \\
&\quad (CC_t \geq 0, OC_t \geq 0)
\end{aligned}$$

2.2 Space - What makes the difference in space overcome?

Regional economic attributes are made up of 5 factors.

- Producing economic outputs - What and When
- Consuming economic outputs - What and When
- Prosperity - How[2]

In a mathematical sense, it could be modeled into supplier S , demander D and market governor G for a transaction.

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= \{MP \mid^{\forall} MP \text{ want to sell Product } P \text{ in } \exists M\} \\
D &= \{MP \mid^{\forall} MP \text{ want to buy Product } P \text{ in } \exists M\} \\
G &= \bigcup_n^{N(\{m|m \text{ is } \forall M\})} R_{M_n}
\end{aligned}$$

A transaction occurs when the supplier and demander have a zero actualization time to be realized.

$$\begin{aligned}
TTU_{MP,T} &= \sum_n^{N(MP)} MST(MP, ME_n, M) \cdot TTU_{MP,T} \cdot Lorenz_{MP,ME_n} \\
&\quad \cdot (1 - OE(T))(1 - ME(T))(1 - PE(T)) \\
\text{Optimal } t_{wanted}^* &= \arg \max_t TTU_{MP,T} \\
\text{Optimal } t_{actual}^* &= \arg \max_t (TTU_{MP,T} - CC_t + OC_t) \\
&\quad (CC_t \geq 0, OC_t \geq 0) \\
&\quad \arg \max_t (TTU_{MP,T} - CC_t + OC_t) \approx 0 \Rightarrow^{\exists} T
\end{aligned}$$

So to pay the price for what we choose in freedom for prosperity, humans have started inter-regional cooperation and dispute for the expansion of regional freedoms[3]. There are two kinds of freedoms for freedom – collaboration and dispute.

There can be two cases of regional disputes.

- When disputing expands the prosperity of the region rather than concessions and compromises
- When the prosperity of the region is expanded at the cost of the disastrous consequences of giving up peace

Disputes in regions in period t mean that there can't be direct transactions between the market participants in period t .

There can be two cases for regional collaborations.

- When concessions and compromises expand the freedom of the region rather than conflict
- When the protection of peace expands the freedom of the region without disastrous consequences

There are two ways of collaboration for economic freedom. One is by cooperation, and the other is by competition[4].

So rationally, there are two ways of cooperating for economic freedom.

- For the production and consumption of more diverse economic outputs through integration
- For faster production and consumption of economic outputs through integration

On the other hand, there are two reasons for competition for economic freedom.

- For the production and consumption of more diverse economic outputs through competition
- For the production and consumption of economic output faster through competition

Collaborations and competitions in regions in period t means that there can be direct transactions between the market participants in period t . So, by definition, any direct transactions involved in dispute regions cannot be sustained. And the condition when transactions can not be placed in forms like this:

$$Dispute(t, MP_x, MP_y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } MP_x, MP_y \text{ in dispute} \\ \infty & \text{if } \neg(MP_x, MP_y \text{ in dispute}) \end{cases}$$

And by applying it to the transaction condition, the equation would be formed like this:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\arg \max_t ((TTU_{MP,T} - CC_t + OC_t) \\
&\quad \cdot \left(\sum_n^{N(\forall MP)} \sum_m^{N(\forall MP)} Dispute(t, MP_n, MP_m) \right)) \approx 0 \Rightarrow^{\exists} T
\end{aligned}$$

2.2.1 Establishment of trade and transactions between foreign currencies

Currency is a payment unit for price[5]. And it assembles the social utility measured in one period subsection[6]. Market governor G sets the directions of currency in the total market by the rules in period t . Currency amount C is a currency amount of Market M in period t . Currency Inflater $CI_{R_M,t}$ is set by a set of rules R in market M in period t . Marginal Utility function MU gets marginal utility by transaction T in a unit of price in period t . Economic growth rate EGR is affected by Investment I in period t of market participant MP .

$$C_{\forall MP,t} = \sum_n^{N(\forall T)} MU(T,t)$$

$$C_{\forall MP,t} = \sum_n^{N(\forall MP)} C_{MP_n,t} \cdot (CI_{R_{MP_n,t}} + EGR(t, MP_n, I(t, \forall MP)))$$

In regional cooperation and competition units, product-level exchange is done through production and consumption agreements[7]. And trading level exchange is done through trade agreements[8]. And monetary exchange is done through international monetary agreements[9] or capital agreements by domestic law. They become the elements in a set of rules R .

And by applying it to the transaction condition with the total amount of currency, the Currency Inflater CI with EGR would be by this form:

$$\text{Assuming that period } t_1 < t_2$$

$$CI_{R_{MP_n,t_1}} + EGR(t_1, MP_n, I) \approx \frac{C_{\forall MP,t_2}}{C_{\forall MP,t_1}}$$

2.2.2 Perspective of Market

They are the same in that they are market participants, but they have their own characteristics in their position.

A market entity consists of people. And we will follow the types of market entities in macroeconomics. There are market participants like government (usually supervisors)[10], households(usually suppliers and demanders)[11], corporations(usually suppliers)[11], and foreign entities(usually demanders and suppliers)[11].

Households mainly supply labor and consume products. So, they are suppliers of the labor market and demanders of the product in the production market. Corporations are demanders of the labor market and suppliers of the product in the production market. Foreign entities could be both demanders and suppliers in all of the needs. Government is a market entity of demand and supply by tax and regulation.

Government imposes taxes and regulates the entities of their labor income, property, and consumption. So, based on tax impose rate TIR tax and regulation effects on a transaction by the market like this:

$$\text{Assuming}$$

$$M_X = \text{Market } X$$

$$M_X \text{ Transaction } MT_t = \{T \mid (T \text{ in } t \text{ is } MP_x) \in M_X\}$$

$$\text{Income and Consumption of } MP_x \text{ in } M_X = \text{Total Revenue } TR_{MP_x, M_X}$$

$$= \sum_n^{N(MT_{n,t})} MU(MT_n, t_{MT_n,t})$$

$$\text{Tax}_{M_x}(MP_{M_x}, TR_{MP_x, M_X}) = TR_{MP_x, M_X} \cdot TIR_{M_x}(MP_{M_x}, TR_{MP_x, M_X})$$

2.3 Time – Difference in speed

2.3.1 Why should the economy grow?

What is economic growth? In simple words, economic growth refers to when overall social utility is enhanced[12].

$$\left(EGR((t_1), MP_n, I(t_1, MP)) + \frac{C_{MP, (t_2)}}{C_{MP, (t_1)}} \right) \cdot \sum_n^{N(\{T|T \text{ in } t_1\})} TTU(MP, T_n) \approx \sum_m^{N(\{T|T \text{ in } t_2\})} TTU(MP, T_m)$$

$$EGR(t_1, \forall MP, I(t_1, \forall MP)) > 0 \Rightarrow \text{Economic Growth}$$

In macroeconomics' view, there can be five positions. As for the government (usually supervisors) position, the position changes by agreeing on handling the social benefits gained through supervision. As for households' (usually consumers and suppliers) position, the position changes by maximizing the social utility obtained through income and consumption again at the following income and consumption. As for corporations' (usually producers') position, the position changes by maximizing the social utility obtained through production to the next production. As for banks' (usually corporations with monetary specialty) position, the position changes through how and how much they achieve the purpose of selling the financial products again to the subsequent earnings. And lastly, as for the overseas (usually consumers and producers) position, the position changes by maximizing the social utility obtained by linking different markets to the next production and consumption.

$$\text{Optimal } I^*(t, \forall MP) = \arg \max_{I(t, \forall MP)} EGR(t, \forall MP, I(t, \forall MP))$$

2.3.2 Factors for Economic Growth

Basic factors for economic growth that have been identified as important[13] include:

- Less corruption[14]
- Securing property[15]
- Rule of law[16]
- Better performance of public and private contracts[17]
- Advanced financial capitalism system[18]
- Less murder[19]
- Government efficiency[20]
- Moderated inflation[21]
- Smooth circulation of capital[22]
- Free trade[23]
- Flexible exchange rate[24]
- Education[25]

These factors are related to economic growth, as achieved by maximizing every moment of opportunity within the given freedom.

2.4 Welfare - Solving human's problem

Human beings have equal opportunity and freedom to have rights and obligations intrinsic to human happiness based on arithmetic values such as labor and possessions. Labor is the right of a person to exchange the ownership of their time for work for their intrinsic happiness. Ownership is the right or obligation to assert a right to a particular attribute.

Judging from the definition above, people can face three sets of problems in capitalism based on liberal democracy.

- Problem of labor
- Problem of possession
- Problem of intrinsic happiness

Welfare is a liberal democratic method that helps solve problems difficult to solve by markets. To solve the issues, it can be said that welfare takes a form of government expenditure. And as investment and welfare grow, they have an incremental consideration of productivity p . Consequently, welfare and investment take the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta EGR(t, {}^\forall MP, I(t, {}^\forall MP)) - \Delta CI_{R_{MPn}, t} &= p^\forall MP \cdot \frac{\Delta I(t, {}^\forall MP)}{\Delta C^\forall MP, t} \\ &= p_{MP_{Labor}} \cdot \frac{\Delta I(t, MP_{Labor})}{\Delta C^\forall MP_{Labor}, t} + p_{MP_{Product}} \cdot \frac{\Delta I(t, MP_{Product})}{\Delta C^\forall MP_{Product}, t} + p_{QoL} \cdot \frac{\Delta I(t, QoL)}{\Delta C^\forall QoL, t} \end{aligned}$$

Likewise, the fundamental mathematical model of a transaction-based economic growth framework could be suggested as the law and economics.

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